

**The first record of *Aegomorphus obscurior*
(Pic, 1904) (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae:
Lamiinae) from Ukraine**

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The genus *Aegomorphus* Haldeman, 1847 is represented by five species in the Palaearctic fauna, four of them occur in Europe, and only one is known from Ukraine: *Aegomorphus clavipes* (Schrank, 1781), Transpalaearctic species widespread in all natural territories of the country (Danilevsky, 2018; Bartenev, 2009). While treating the longhorn beetles of South-Eastern Ukraine in the collection of Martynov & Pisarenko (2004), a specimen of *Aegomorphus obscurior* (Pic, 1904) was found among the specimens of *A. clavipes*. This is the first record of this species from Ukraine. The specimen (Fig. 1) is deposited in the collection of authors (Donetsk, Ukraine).

Fig. 1. *Aegomorphus obscurior* (Pic, 1904), habitus, female.

***Aegomorphus obscurior* (Pic, 1904)**

Aegomorphus wojtylai Hilszczański et Bystrowski, 2005

Material examined: Ukraine: Luhansk Region, Luhansk Natural Reserve, Stanichno-Luhanske branch, 48.7570°N 39.3584°E, 08.06.2000, 1 ♀ (V. V. Martynov).

Aegomorphus obscurior differs from closely related *A. clavipes* by reduced white pubescence before transverse white central elytral band, wider, relatively flatter and obliquely apically truncated parameres and short, broader base of posterior tegmen appendage (Hilszczański & Bystrowski, 2005; Danilevsky & Shapovalov, 2007). It was described from Poland and now it is also known from Latvia, European Russia (Moscow, Ryazan, and Orenburg Regions), West Siberia (Chelyabinsk, Omsk Regions, Altai Krai), East Siberia (south of Krasnoyarsk Krai, Irkutsk Region), Russian Far East (Amur Region, Primorsky Krai), Eastern Kazakhstan, Mongolia and Japan (Danilevsky & Shapovalov, 2007; Hilszczański, 2008; Danilevsky, 2018). In all known localities *A. obscurior* is sympatric with *A. clavipes* (Danilevsky & Shapovalov, 2007).

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